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ANALYSIS OF THE SIGNIFICANCE OF BREEDING OF MUNGBEAN
CULTIVARS AND SAMPLES BY DIALLEL CROSSING METHOD

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada diallel chatishitish usulida moshning nav va namunalarining seleksion ahamiyati o'rganilgan. Tadqiqotlarda moshning ikkita xorijiy va ikkita mahalliy navlari qatnashgan hamda ular ortasida diallel chatishish qobilyati aniqlangan. Diallel chatishtirish olib borishdan maqsad xorijiy va mahalliy mosh navlarining o'z-aro chatishish qobilyatini aniqlash va seleksiya jarayoni uchun qimmatli xo'jalik belgilariga ega bo'lgan namunalarni aniqlashdan iborat. Tadqiqotlar asosan Griffing metodikasi asosida olib borildi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, Osiyo × VI-062909 – 47%, Osiyo × VI-060020 A-G – 47%, Durdona × VI-060020 A-G – 47% kombinatsiyalarida eng yuqori ko'rsatkishlar qayd etildi. Bu duragaylar kelgusida ilmiy tadqiqotlarda va genetik amaliyotlarda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: mosh, nav, namuna, diallel chatishtirish, kombinatsiya, duragay avlod, dukkak, irsiylanish

Аннотация. В данной статье изучается селекционная ценность сортов и образцов маша с использованием метода диаллельного скрещивания. В исследовании были задействованы два зарубежных и два местных сорта маша, и определена их способность к диаллельному скрещиванию. Цель проведения диаллельного скрещивания – определить способность зарубежных и местных сортов маша к скрещиванию и выявить образцы с ценными экономическими признаками для процесса селекции. Исследование проводилось в основном по методу Гриффинга. По результатам исследования, самые высокие показатели были зафиксированы в комбинациях Osiyo × VI-062909 – 47%, Osiyo × VI-060020 A-G – 47%, Durdona × VI-060020 A-G – 47%. Эти гибриды имеют большое значение для будущих научных исследований и генетической практики.

Ключевые слова: маш, сорт, образец, диаллельное скрещивание, комбинация, гибридное поколение, бобовые, наследование

Abstract. This article examines the selection value of mungbean cultivars and samples using the method of diallel crossing. The study involved two foreign and two local cultivars of mungbean, and their ability by means of diallel crossing was determined. The aim of the diallel crossing was to determine the ability of foreign and local mungbean cultivars to cross and identify samples with valuable economic characteristics for the breeding process. The research was conducted primarily using the Griffing method. The study found that the highest rates were recorded in the combinations Osiyo × VI-062909, Osiyo × VI-060020 A-G and Durdona × VI-060020 A-G, all at 47%. There are great importance of these hybrids for future scientific research and genetic practice.

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Keywords: mungbean, cultivars, sample, diallel crossing, combination, hybrid generation, legumes, inheritance

INTRODUCTION

Among leguminous crops, mungbean is considered one of the most important nutritional crops and is grown in almost all regions of Uzbekistan. Mungbean grain is distinguished by its rapid digestion and the presence of protein in its composition. Today, it is urgent to create cultivars with high yield, good quality and resistance to diseases and pests for agriculture. In the selection process, the method of diallel crossing is used to study the genetic characteristics of cultivars and samples and determine their combinatory ability. In the parental samples selected through diallel crossing, the degree of heritability of characters and properties in subsequent generations is clearly manifested. This makes it possible to select valuable hybrids for creating new cultivars in the selection process. The purpose of this study is to analyze mungbean cultivars and samples using the diallel crossing method and identify promising combinations for selection practices.

S. Saima., G. Li., G. Wular [76 ; 481-492-p.]. In their scientific research, seven hybrid combinations of mungbeans were studied, and they used polyethylene glycol to artificially create drought for mungbean combinations. This substance limits the ability of mung beans to easily consume water, which is how drought is created. In their research, they mainly evaluated the following indicators.

- Planting stress tolerance index
- Stem and root weight
- Root length stress index
- Dry matter stress index
- Plant height stress index

In mungbean hybrid combinations, there were some negative effects due to drought on the mentioned indicators. However, the root mass and root length stress index increased. Since water is located in deep layers, the root system begins to develop strongly in drought conditions. This is a natural adaptation mechanism of the varieties.

According to the studies of G. Singh et al. [77; 2376-2378-p.], when an 8×8 diallel analysis experiment was conducted on 13 quantitative traits in mungbean varieties, high efficiency was found in general combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA). In particular, the hybrids Pusa Baisakhi × Pusa Bold (Vishal), Pant Mung-1 × ML-613, Pant M-3 × PS-16 and Pusa Bold (Vishal) × ML-613 had positive results in terms of the number of nodes on the main stem, the number of pods per plant, the amount of protein in the seed and the seed yield per plant.

J. D Patel et al. [66; 433-443-p.]. Forty-four different mungbean genotypes were described and grouped based on morphological characteristics. According to the results of the study, the genotypes differed significantly in terms of flowering time, with the earliest flowering observed at 37.33 days (GJM 1011) and the latest

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flowering at 53.67 days (Pant M-3). According to this characteristic, the genotypes were divided into early flowering (EC 482907 and GJM 1011), mid-term flowering (41 genotypes) and late flowering (only Pant M-3) groups. In terms of plant height, the K 851 genotype was the shortest, 12 genotypes had long plant height, and the remaining 31 genotypes had medium height. Pubescence was observed in all genotypes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Field experiments were conducted in the small experimental area of the Karakalpakstan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies. Two foreign (VI-062909 and VI-060020 A-G) and two local cultivars and samples (Durdona and Osiyo) of mungbean were placed in a nursery in a 60x15x1 scheme. In the experiments, the planting processes, biometric measurements and phenological observations of crops were carried out based on the methods and recommendations of B. A. Dospekhov "Methodology of field experience" (1985). The involvement of mungbean varieties and samples in diallel crossing was carried out based on the method of B. Griffing "Concept of general and specific combining ability in relation to diallel crossing systems" (Australia, 1956).

Diallelic crosses between varieties and samples of mungbean were conducted based on the following combinations: (1-table)

1-table

Combinations involved in diallel crossing

No	Combinations	No	Combinations
1	VI-060020 A-G x Durdona	7	VI- 062909 x Durdona
2	VI-060020 A-G x VI- 062909	8	VI- 062909 x Osiyo
3	VI-060020 A-G x Osiyo	9	VI- 062909 x VI-060020 A-G
4	Osiyo x Durdona	10	Durdona x VI- 062909
5	Osiyo x VI- 062909	11	Durdona x Osiyo
6	Osiyo x VI-060020 A-G	12	Durdona x VI-060020 A-G

RESEARCH RESULTS

Genetic analysis and cross-breeding methods are widely used in the creation of new, high-yielding, ecologically adapted varieties of mung bean (*Vigna radiata* L.). The diallel cross-breeding method is one of the most effective approaches in this regard, which determines the general combining ability and specific combining ability of cultivars and hybrids, which represent hereditary traits.

As part of the cross-breeding experiment, 15 flowers in each combination were artificially pollinated, and the number of pollinated and unpollinated flowers, as well as the number of pods formed but not fully formed, i.e., inflorescent, were recorded separately. The results of the analysis show that a total of 180 flowers were pollinated across all 12 cross-breeding combinations. Of these, 67 were pollinated (37%), 82 were unpollinated, resulting in a total of 31 inflorescent pods. These pods were not biologically fully formed, with no seeds developed inside, and their percentage was

17%. This indicator reflects the degree of sterility, rather than complete fertilization, among the cultivars participating in the diallel cross.

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In the combinations VI-060020 A-G × VI-062909, Osiyo × Durдона, Durдона × VI-062909 and Durдона × Osiyo, out of almost 15 flowers, correspondingly 6 were pollinated, 6, 8 and 7 were not pollinated, 3, 1 and 2 were sterile. The proportion of pollinated flowers in all three combinations was 40%, which is a relatively high pollination rate in these combinations.

In the combinations VI-060020 A-G × Osiyo and VI-062909 × Durдона, respectively 5 flowers were pollinated, 5 and 8 were not pollinated, 5 and 2 were formed as sterile pods. The pollination rate in the two combinations was 33%, which indicates an average efficiency. The relatively high number of sterile pods may indicate genetic imbalance.

In the combinations Durдона × VI-060020 A-G, Osiyo × VI-060020 A-G and Osiyo × VI-062909, 7 flowers were pollinated, 8, 6 and 5 were not pollinated, respectively. The number of sterile pods was almost the same in the combinations, but the overall pollination rate of 47% was recorded as a high indicator.

The highest pollination efficiency indicators are:

Osiyo × VI-062909 – 47%

Osiyo × VI-060020 A-G – 47%

Durдона × VI-060020 A-G – 47%

These combinations indicate good genetic compatibility and can be considered promising for future breeding work.

Combinations with the lowest pollination rate:

VI-060020 A-G × Durдона – 27%

VI-062909 × Osiyo – 27%

VI-062909 × VI-060020 A-G – 27%

These combinations are characterized by a relatively high number of sterile pods and a large number of unpollinated flowers. In these cases, the probability of seed failure is high, indicating genetic imbalance. (2-table)

2-table

Diallel cross data in mungbean cultivars and samples

Crossing combinations	Miqdoriy malumotlar				The emerging mungbeans %
	Number of pollinated specimens	Polinated flowers	Unpollinated flowers	Steril pods	
VI-060020 A-G x Durдона	15	4	6	5	27 %
VI-060020 A-G x VI-062909	15	6	6	3	40 %
VI-060020 A-G x Osiyo	15	5	5	5	33 %
Osiyo x Durдона	15	6	7	2	40 %
Osiyo x VI-	15	7	5	3	47 %

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062909					
Osiyo x VI-060020 A-G	15	7	6	2	47 %
VI- 062909 x Durdona	15	5	8	2	33 %
VI- 062909 x Osiyo	15	4	7	4	27 %
VI- 062909 x VI-060020 A-G	15	4	9	2	27 %
Durdona x VI-062909	15	6	8	1	40 %
Durdona x Osiyo	15	6	7	2	40 %
Durdona x VI-060020 A-G	15	7	8		47 %
Jami	180	67	82	31	37 %

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the results of the general analysis, 67 of the pollinated flowers, i.e. 37%, were effectively pollinated, indicating the presence of genetic compatibility in these combinations. At the same time, 82 flowers (46%) remained unpollinated, indicating a low response to pollination in these combinations. One of the noteworthy aspects is that 31 flowers (17%) developed in the form of sterile pods, which, despite the external formation of these pods, did not produce seeds. High indicators were observed in the combinations Durdona × VI-060020 A-G, Osiyo × VI-060020 A-G and Osiyo × VI-062909. It would be advisable to use these combinations as starting materials in future breeding processes and genetic studies.

REFERENCES:

1. Доспехов В. А. Методика полевого опыта.-Москва.: Kolos, 1985.-С. 317.
<https://arm.ssuv.uz/frontend/web/books/652527ba2ddf1.pdf>
 2. Griffing B. Concept of general and specific combining ability in relation to diallel crossing systems // *Australian Journal of Biological Sciences*. – 1956.–Т.9,№4.–P.463–493.
https://jpp.journals.ekb.eg/article_253316_6af3a216797538ac7fcd4dfdda314fe5.pdf
 3. Patel J.D., Patel J.B., Chetariya C.P. Characterization of Mung bean (*Vigna radiata* L. Wilczek) Genotypes Based on Plant Morphology // *Indian Journal of Pure & Applied Biosciences*. - India, 2019. - 4-oktyabr. - Vol. 7, No. 5. - P. 433-443. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18782/2320-7051.7793>
 4. Singh G., Prasad B.K., Monu Kumar, Anuj Kumar. Diallel analysis in mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek) // *The Pharma Innovation Journal*. - India, 2021.-5-noyabr.-Vol.10, No.-12. - P. 2376-2378.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357966405_Diallel_analysis_in_mungbean_Vigna_radiata_L_Wilczek
- Saimi S., Li G., Wu. G. Effects of drought stress on hybrids of *Vigna radiata* at germination stage// *Acta Biologica Hungarica*. - 2018.- Vol.69.- P. 481-492.
<https://akjournals.com/view/journals/018/69/4/article-p481.pdf>